

Flexible operation of a Small Modular Reactor for combined hydrogen and electricity production

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ABSTRACT

In a Nuclear Hybrid Energy System (NHES), nuclear reactors can be coupled to hydrogen production systems to meet the growing demand for low-carbon hydrogen. This work investigates the integration of a light-water cooled SMR with a high-temperature steam electrolysis hydrogen production plant via an intermediate heat transfer loop. A dynamic simulator of the NHES architecture, developed in the object-oriented modelling language Modelica, is applied to assess the dynamic response of the system in three different operational strategies, namely *reactor-follows*, *hydrogen-follows*, and *reactor-hydrogen-follows*. These modes differ in how nuclear reactor power and hydrogen production are coordinated to meet highly variable grid demands. The simulation outcomes indicate that the *reactor-hydrogen-follows* philosophy enables the system to accommodate highly variable grid ramp rates, up to 15%/min, while maintaining both the reactor and the electrolyser within the allowed operational limits. Overall, the analysis demonstrates that coupling nuclear and hydrogen systems can significantly enhance the overall system flexibility, a key requirement in the evolving power sector characterised by the increasing penetration of non-programmable renewable sources.

Keywords: Nuclear hybrid energy system, Small Modular Reactor, Hydrogen, Flexibility, Dynamic model

1. INTRODUCTION

Among low-carbon hydrogen production technologies, electrolysis plays a major role. Electrolysers enable hydrogen production by driving the water-splitting reactor with an electrical power input. Provided that the latter comes from a clean electricity source, electrolysis allows meeting the pressing need for low-carbon hydrogen. Low-temperature electrolysers, such as alkaline or proton exchange membrane electrolysers, stand out as the most mature technology. Another hydrogen production technology that is gaining interest is High-Temperature Steam Electrolysis (HTSE), which requires heat input to vaporise process water. Among HTSE technologies, Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells (SOEC) are the most mature options [1]. In these systems, the water splitting reaction occurs at temperatures between 650°C and 900°C [2]. HTSE has a lower technology readiness level compared to low-temperature electrolysis; however, thanks to the higher operating temperature, it offers significantly higher electrical efficiency, lowering the power input for the same hydrogen production [2].

Nuclear energy, as a low-carbon and programmable energy source, is emerging as a possible contributor to sustain the increasing need for large-scale hydrogen production. As of today, there are limited experiences of nuclear-based hydrogen production, mainly involving small-scale hydrogen production for internal uses, such as in the case of the Oskarshamn nuclear power plant in Sweden, where the produced hydrogen is used for generator cooling [3]. Nevertheless, several demonstration projects are either under deployment or have been announced to showcase the viability of coupling the power plant's operation with the hydrogen production process [3, 4, 5].

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A coupling between the nuclear reactor and the hydrogen production plant can be achieved in a so-called Nuclear Hybrid Energy System (NHES). In these systems, the nuclear reactor is interconnected with other energy sources, such as renewables, energy storage systems, and non-electric applications, to produce a range of commodities beyond electricity, such as heat, hydrogen, synthetic fuels, or desalinated water [6]. These systems are characterised by high flexibility, since the produced power can be dynamically allocated to either grid power supply or to industrial processes according to commodity demands and market conditions [6]. In this regard, when integrated into an NHES, the operational paradigm of the nuclear reactor can fundamentally change. Traditionally, Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) are operated as baseload generators; nonetheless, some reactors, notably in France, have successfully implemented load-following strategies to respond to grid requirements. The flexible operation of NPPs is limited by several technical constraints [7] which limit the rate of thermal power change to a maximum of about 5% per minute [8]. Moreover, from an economic standpoint, it is generally more advantageous to operate the reactor at full power, leveraging high capacity factors. In contrast, within an NHES, the reactor can be maintained under rated conditions while the overall system's flexible operation is achieved through coordination among the interconnected subsystems. For instance, in the load-following by cogeneration mode, the nuclear reactor operates at nominal thermal power, and variations in grid requirements are accommodated by adjusting the heat extraction to drive non-electrical applications [9].

In this study, a dynamic simulator of a NHES architecture encompassing a light-water cooled Small Modular Reactor (SMR) and HTSE-based hydrogen production plant is applied to investigate different operational strategies to enhance grid flexibility. Three operational philosophies are analysed: the *reactor-follows* strategy, with the nuclear reactor power modulated to meet grid demands; *hydrogen-follows*, where the reactor operates at rated conditions and flexibility is achieved by regulating hydrogen production; and the combined *reactor-hydrogen-follows*, where both subsystems share the duty of flexible operation. Dynamic simulations on an illustrative transient scenario are performed to assess the technical viability of meeting highly variable grid requirements in these three operational strategies, leveraging the thermal and electrical interconnection between the NPP and the hydrogen production system. The comparison focuses on critical variables in both systems, such as temperature variations in the electrolyser and power ramps in the nuclear core.

2. NHES DESIGN AND OPERATION

A schematic of the reference architecture is shown in Figure 1. The NPP, encompassing the Nuclear Steam Supply System (NSSS) and its Balance Of Plant (BOP), is coupled to multiple HTSE modules via an intermediate heat transfer loop. The selected nuclear technology considered for this NHES is a light-water cooled, pressurized water-type SMR. In particular, the European SMR (E-SMR) conceptual design, developed within the framework of the Euratom-funded ELSMOR project [10], is selected for this study. The operational rated conditions of the reactor are reported in Table I.

Table I. E-SMR module design parameters [10].

Parameter	Value	Unit
Nominal thermal power	540	MW _{th}
Nominal net electrical power	170	MW _{el}
Primary coolant pressure	150	bar
Core inlet temperature	300	°C
Core outlet temperature	324.5	°C
Steam pressure	45	bar
Feedwater inlet temperature	163	°C
Steam outlet temperature	300	°C

A simplified BOP architecture, featuring one high-pressure and one low-pressure pre-heater, is adopted in this work. Steam at 300°C and 45 bar is extracted from the steam generator outlet and diverted to an intermediate heat exchanger. Here, the steam is condensed and returned to the deaerator, while thermal oil flowing in the intermediate loop is heated to 250°C and evenly distributed to the HTSE modules that compose the hydrogen production plant. Although these temperature levels are significantly higher than those required by the water evaporation process in the HTSE, this extraction point is selected as a conservative assumption, since extraction from the main steam line is expected to have the highest impact on reactor operation compared with extractions at other points along the turbine line. In further studies, the extraction point should be optimised to maximise overall system performance. In case of partial load operation of the hydrogen production system, a fraction of the total oil flow rate is bypassed to respond to the reduced thermal power requirements of the HTSE modules. In the HTSE system, shown on the right-hand side of Figure 1, the flow is used for process water vaporisation and an initial superheating phase to 150°C. The required temperature of the water-splitting reaction, assumed to be 750°C in this architecture, is achieved through a sequence of recuperative heat exchangers (CAT-HX, AN-HX) and electrical heaters (CAT-eHTR, AN-eHTR).

The NHES architecture is sized to allocate the whole reactor power to hydrogen production, i.e., without supplying electricity to the grid. As a result, the HTSE capacity is defined to be able to absorb the whole steam cycle power generation, accounting for the power loss driven by heat extraction to meet the hydrogen production plant's thermal power requirements. This, in turn, is used to determine the intermediate loop transmission capacity. Under these conditions, the hydrogen production system absorbs approximately 38 MW_{th} of thermal power and 160 MW_{el} of electrical power, resulting in a hydrogen output of about 108 t_{H₂}/day.

Figure 1. Schematic of the considered NHES architecture.

In this work, several operational philosophies are considered, aimed at enhancing the flexible operation by leveraging the multi-purpose nature of the plant, i.e., by coordinating the operation of the integrated system to meet variable grid requirements. In this regard, three operational philosophies are discussed:

- *Reactor-follows*: In this strategy, the nuclear reactor is responsible for sustaining all the flexibility requirements of the system. The reactor power is dynamically allocated either to grid electricity supply or to hydrogen generation, according to the independent production targets of the two commodities.
- *Hydrogen-follows*: The hydrogen production plant accommodates the flexible operation requirements, enabling the reactor to operate steadily at rated conditions, in line with the load-following cogeneration mode. As a result, all the excess thermal and electrical power produced by the reactor is allocated to the hydrogen production plant.

- *Reactor-hydrogen-follows*: This approach considers a combination of the previous operational philosophies. Rapid grid fluctuations are accommodated by modulating the reactor power within the allowed limits (i.e., 5%/min), while the remainder is satisfied by regulating the operation of the hydrogen production plant. As a result, it is possible to reduce the shift in the off-design regime of both the nuclear reactor and the HTSE modules.

It is worth highlighting that these control strategies aim at increasing the flexible operation from a grid perspective. However, other operational philosophies can be adopted if hydrogen is the prioritised commodity: in this case, a *grid-follows* strategy could be implemented, maintaining the reactor power at rated conditions while meeting variable hydrogen loads by delivering excess electricity to the power grid.

3. NHES SIMULATOR

The overall simulator of the NHES architecture, shown in Figure 2, has been developed in the object-oriented modelling language Modelica, leveraging its advantages to simulate complex, integrated energy systems [11]: among these, it is possible to flexibly assemble models from existing libraries into the overall NHES simulator, adopting a plug-and-play approach. In this study, the NSSS, BOP, and intermediate loop models available in the open-source *TANDEM* library [12] were connected to the dynamic simulator of an HTSE module, which in turn is based on components from the *ThermoPower* library [13].

Figure 2. Dynamic simulator of the NHES architecture.

All considered subsystems are based on a one-dimensional modelling approach, with the aim of accounting for dynamic and inertial effects in both the single components and in the thermal interconnections between them. In particular, for the NSSS, the core relies on point kinetics equations for the neutronics and an equilibrium pressurizer model [14]. Moreover, for the HTSE module, it is important to use a one-dimensional electrolyser model capable of capturing temperature gradients and local temperature variations. Each NHES component has a dedicated control block, encompassing several

Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers calibrated to maintain key process variables within the allowed operational limits adopting a decentralised control approach [14]. These control blocks can be replaced by the user to test case-specific control strategies to investigate the response of the system in different operational philosophies. In this work, the aforementioned control approaches were implemented, acting mainly on the BOP and HTSE controllers, while a conventional temperature control programme has been selected for the NSSS. This choice is motivated by the strict regulatory requirements governing the primary side operation; consequently, a standardised and well-established control scheme, based on a constant average core temperature program, is adopted.

4. CASE STUDIES AND SIMULATION OUTCOMES

This section delves into the operational philosophies introduced before, discussing the proposed approach and impact on key operational variables of both the nuclear and hydrogen production plants. An overview of the numerical outcomes is provided in Section 4.4. In each case study, the same grid requirements are imposed: at the starting point, the reactor is assumed to operate at rated conditions, delivering 20% of the steam cycle's rated electricity generation of about 175 MW_{el} to the grid and allocating the remaining thermal and electrical power for hydrogen production. After 15 minutes, the power output to the grid is ramped down at 10%/min to zero and then ramped back up to 10% at the same rate.

4.1. Reactor-follows

In this operational strategy, all the flexibility requirements are met by modulating the reactor power, as in the conventional load-following mode. The hydrogen production rate remains constantly at 80% rated capacity, reflecting the typical need of industrial processes of having a stable hydrogen supply. It is worth highlighting that this operational strategy is reported exclusively for the sake of comparison with other case studies, as in a realistic scenario the reactor power alone would not be allowed to undertake such rapid power variations. The dynamic simulation outcomes are displayed in Figure 3. The electrical power flows on the left-hand side show how the whole grid variability is met by adjusting the steam cycle power generation, i.e., the reactor thermal power allocated to power conversion, as the thermal and electrical power flows delivered to the hydrogen production plant remain constant. The rapid grid variation requires substantial reactivity adjustments to keep the average core temperature within limits, leading to minor power oscillations before reaching the new steady-state conditions.

Figure 3. System response in the reactor-follows strategy.

4.2. Hydrogen-follows

The *hydrogen-follows* philosophy is the implementation of the aforementioned load-following by cogeneration mode: here, the core power remains at rated conditions, and hydrogen production is modulated to meet grid requirements. The stable reactor operation is illustrated on the right-hand side of Figure 4, with a minimal fraction extracted for the HTSE's thermal requirements and the remainder exploited for power conversion. As shown on the left-hand side, the steam cycle generation experiences minor variations, driven by the varying thermal requirements of the hydrogen production plant, which, in turn, will affect the BOP power generation. As the whole responsibility for flexible operation is shifted to the HTSE, it is fundamental that the operational constraints (e.g., temperature gradients and variation rates that can lead to thermal stresses in the cell) are always respected during transient conditions.

Figure 4. System response in the hydrogen-follows strategy.

4.3. Reactor-hydrogen-follows

In the last operational philosophy, the modulation of both the nuclear reactor and HTSE is coordinated, with the aim of meeting the reactor operational constraint of a maximal ramping rate of 5%/min and reducing the burden of the flexible operation on the cell's solid structure. In particular, during the transient interval, the hydrogen production is modulated at a rate of 5%/min, with the remainder accommodated by variations in reactor power. The advantage of this approach is twofold: on the one hand, it mitigates the ramping rates on the individual subsystems; on the other hand, it reduces core power and hydrogen production excursions compared to the *reactor-follows* and *hydrogen-follows*, respectively.

4.4. Comparison between cases

Table II summarises the key technical indicators, e.g., in terms of variation rates, resulting from the dynamic simulation. The *reactor-hydrogen-follows* case was extended to even more rapid variations in grid requirements, with the aim of investigating if they could be met without compromising the normal operation of the reactor or the HTSE modules. Overall, it can be seen how the whole flexibility requirements, both in terms of power variation and ramping rates, are met either by the hydrogen production plant or by the nuclear reactor in the first two cases. In the *hydrogen-follows* the maximal temperature variation rate achieved in the cell's nodes is 3°C/min, which is typically considered the maximal acceptable limit [15]. For the same grid ramp rate, this indicator is significantly lower in the *reactor-hydrogen-follows*, due to the limited variation in hydrogen generation (both in magnitude and variation speed). According to the simulation outcomes presented in Table II, the system could meet even higher flexibility requirements, i.e., variations of 15%/min, maintaining both the reactor and the HTSE within the allowed limits. For higher ramping rates in the hydrogen production plants, which would be neces-

Figure 5. System response in the combined reactor-hydrogen-follows strategy.

sary for grid power variations of 20%/min, the temperature variation rate in the cell would be too high, suggesting that other measures to modulate power generation or hydrogen production (e.g., activation of steam bypass systems), should be explored.

Table II. Summary of SMR and HTSE dynamic responses in different operational philosophies.

Parameter	Reactor-follows	H ₂ -follows	Reactor-H ₂ -follows		
Grid ramp rate (%/min)	10	10	10	15	20
HTSE maximal ramp rate (%/min)	0	8.78	4.85	9.57	14.13
HTSE maximal power variation (%)	0	20.16	10	13.33	15
SOE temperature change rate (°C/min)	0	3	1.72	2.98	3.83
SMR maximal ramp rate (%/min)	8.99	0	4.86	4.31	4.07
SMR maximal power variation (%)	18.86	0	10.11	6.44	4.88

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, three operational philosophies of a NHES encompassing a light-water cooled SMR and an HTSE plant for flexible hydrogen and electricity production were investigated, with the aim of assessing its capabilities in satisfying highly flexible grid requirements. The dynamic simulation outcomes, obtained with a model of the overall, integrated system, demonstrated that in the *hydrogen-follows* strategy that variable grid demands can be achieved by maintaining the nuclear reactor stable, but significant thermal stresses can arise in the electrolyser throughout the transient. In contrast, the *reactor-follows* mode requires operating the reactor beyond the allowed operational limits. According to the results, the combined *reactor-hydrogen-follows* proved to be an effective solution to distribute the burden of flexible operation on both the reactor and the electrolyser, thereby mitigating the impact on the two systems. For instance, a 10%/min variation in grid demand could be satisfied with ramping rates on the HTSE and core powers below 5%/min each, remaining within the allowed limits of key operational parameters.

Future developments should address both technical and economic aspects, focusing on the safety of system interconnections and the competitiveness of this configuration with respect to alternative hydrogen and electricity production technologies. In addition, the impact of flexible operation on electrolyser degradation should be assessed, together with the challenges posed by strong operational dependencies between the subsystems, including outage management.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Hauch, R. Küngas, P. Blennow, A. B. Hansen, J. B. Hansen, B. V. Mathiesen, and M. B. Mogensen. "Recent advances in solid oxide cell technology for electrolysis." *Science*, **volume 370**(6513), p. eaba6118 (2020).
- [2] A. Buttler and H. Spliethoff. "Current status of water electrolysis for energy storage, grid balancing and sector coupling via power-to-gas and power-to-liquids: A review." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, **volume 82**, pp. 2440–2454 (2018).
- [3] IAEA. "Hydrogen Production with Operating Nuclear Power Plants - Business Case." Technical report, International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna (2023).
- [4] V. Venizelou and A. Poullikkas. "Comprehensive Overview of Recent Research and Industrial Advancements in Nuclear Hydrogen Production." *Energies*, **volume 17**(12) (2024).
- [5] A. Constantin. "Nuclear hydrogen projects to support clean energy transition: Updates on international initiatives and IAEA activities." *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, **volume 54**, pp. 768–779 (2024).
- [6] IAEA. "Nuclear–Renewable Hybrid Energy Systems." Technical Report Nuclear Energy Series No. NR-T-1.24, International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna (2023).
- [7] R. Ponciroli, Y. Wang, Z. Zhou, A. Botterud, J. Jenkins, R. B. Vilim, and F. Ganda. "Profitability Evaluation of Load-Following Nuclear Units with Physics-Induced Operational Constraints." *Nuclear Technology*, **volume 200**(3), pp. 189–207 (2017).
- [8] Nuclear Energy Agency. *Technical and Economic Aspects of Load Following with Nuclear Power Plants*. Nuclear Development. OECD (2021).
- [9] G. Locatelli, A. Fiordaliso, S. Boarin, and M. E. Ricotti. "Cogeneration: An option to facilitate load following in Small Modular Reactors." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 97**, pp. 153–161 (2017).
- [10] S. Lansou et al. "ELSMOR – towards European Licensing of Small Modular Reactors: Methodology recommendations for light-water small modular reactors safety assessment." *Open Research Europe*, **volume 3**, p. 158 (2023).
- [11] G. C. Masotti, A. Cammi, S. Lorenzi, and M. E. Ricotti. "Modeling and simulation of nuclear hybrid energy systems architectures." *Energy Conversion and Management*, **volume 298**, p. 117684 (2023).
- [12] G. C. Masotti, N. Alpy, A. Baudoux, Y. Hammadi, D. Jouret, S. Lorenzi, S. Mathonnière, G. Simonini, and C. Vaglio-Gaudard. "Modelling Nuclear Hybrid Energy Systems: Objectives, architecture, and applications of the TANDEM Modelica library." *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, **volume 84**, p. 104695 (2025).
- [13] F. Casella and A. Leva. "Modelling of thermo-hydraulic power generation processes using Modelica." *Mathematical and Computer Modelling of Dynamical Systems*, **volume 12**(1), pp. 19–33 (2006).
- [14] G. C. Masotti, S. Lorenzi, and M. E. Ricotti. "Dynamic modelling and control of a Small Modular Reactor in load following by cogeneration mode." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 445**, p. 114518 (2025).
- [15] L. Wehrle, Y. Wang, A. Banerjee, N. Brandon, and O. Deutschmann. "Dynamic Modeling of Reversible Solid Oxide Cells." *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, **volume 91**(6), pp. 833–842 (2019).